

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – AUGUST 2021
(PBM1) STA 221: STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

The table below represents the ages of midwives at Mother and Baby Unit of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital. Represent the information on a histogram diagram and frequency polygon.

Age (years)	30 – 39	40 – 49	50 – 59	60 – 69	70 – 79
Frequency (f)	6	22	38	15	4

- Table - 5 Marks
- Graph - 15 Marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Tabulate three (3) differences between a bar chart and a pie chart - 3 Marks
- b. Tabulate three (3) differences between a bar chart and a histogram - 3 Marks

The data below indicates the ages of patients at the males' ward of the Holy Family Hospital, Berekum. Given the data;

18	20	18	18	24	10	15
12	20	35	14	20	18	24
18	16	16	20	7	2	5

- c. Construct a cumulative frequency distribution table for the data containing class boundaries - 6 Marks
- d. Calculate the median age. - 8 Marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FAMILY NURSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2019
(PBM1) STA 121: STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

The table below represents the ages of midwives at Mother and Baby Unit of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital.

Age (years)	30 – 39	40 – 49	50 – 59	60 – 69	70 – 79
Frequency (f)	6	22	38	15	4

- a. Represent the above information on a histogram.
- Table 5
- Marks
- Graph (Histogram) 10
- Marks
- b. Construct a frequency polygon from the histogram 5
- Marks

Question Two

The table below shows the number of hours obtained by 20 nursing students on the ward.

Number of Hours	40 – 44	45 – 49	50 – 54	55 – 59	60 – 64
Number of Students	2	3	7	6	2

From the table, calculate to two decimal places;

- a. Variance. 11
Marks
- b. Standard deviation 3
Marks
- c. Co-efficient of variation. 6
Marks

Question 3

- a. In a tabular form outline **three (3)** differences between a bar chart and a pie chart. 3
Marks
- b. Tabulate **three (3)** differences between a bar chart and a histogram. 3
Marks

The data below indicates the ages of patients at the males' ward of the Holy Family Hospital, Berekum.

18	20	18	18	24	10	15
12	20	35	14	20	18	24
18	16	16	20	7	2	5

- c. Construct a cumulative frequency distribution table for the data containing class boundaries. 6
Marks
- d. Calculate the median age. 8
Marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FAMILY NURSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE – BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2019

(RGN 20 & RM 15) STA 121: STATISTICS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

The table below represents the ages of midwives at Mother and Baby Unit of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital.

Age (years)	30 – 39	40 – 49	50 – 59	60 – 69	70 – 79
Frequency (f)	6	22	38	15	4

- a. Represent the above information on a histogram.

Table

- 5 Marks

Graph (Histogram)

- 10 Marks

- b. Construct a frequency polygon from the histogram

- 5 Marks

Question Two

The table below shows the number of hours obtained by 20 nursing students on the ward.

Number of Hours	40 – 44	45 – 49	50 – 54	55 - 59	60 – 64
Number of Students	2	3	7	6	2

From the table, calculate to two decimal places;

- a. Variance.

- 11 Marks

- b. Standard deviation.

- 3 Marks

- c. Co-efficient of variation.

- 6 Marks

Question Three

- a. State the four (4) scales of measurement in order of complexity thus from simple to complex. - 2 Marks
- b. Outline any two (2) methods of collecting statistical data. - 2 Marks
- c. Enumerate four (4) properties of a normal distribution. - 4 Marks
- d. A student obtained a raw score of 68 in an examination. If the raw score gives her a T-score of 90, with a class standard deviation known to be 5, what would be the class mean? - 5 Marks
- e. The table below shows the ages of patients at the general ward of the St. Mary's Hospital, Drobo. Calculate to 1 decimal place the modal age. - 5 Marks

Age (years)	5 – 9	10 – 14	15 – 19	20 – 24	25 – 29
Frequency	2	4	8	5	1

- f. Outline one (1) advantage and one (1) disadvantage of the mode - 2 Marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
H FNMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – AUGUST – 2021
(PBM3) STA 121: STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 45MINS
OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

- a. State ANY Three (3) data contained in a statistical table. - 3 Marks
- b. Define the following; - 12 Marks
- (i) statistics
 - (ii) variable
 - (iii) statistic
 - (iv) parameter
 - (v) population
 - (vi) sample
- c) For each of the following variables, indicate whether it is **quantitative** or **qualitative** for quantitative indicate whether **continuous** or **discrete**: - 5 Marks
- i. the number of pairs of shoes you own
 - ii. the type of cars colors
 - iii. where you go on vacation.....
 - iv. the distance it is from your hostel to campus.....
 - v. the number of quizzes you take per school year.....

QUESTION TWO

The following table gives the distribution of the body masses of 180 cancer patients who attended Leticia Homecare Hospital.

Mass (kg)	50-54	55-59	60-64	65-69	70-74	75-79
Frequency	12	18	40	56	30	24

- a. Construct a cumulative frequency table for the distribution - 6 Marks
- b. Use the table to draw an Ogive - 6 marks

Please Turn Over

c. A traffic warden is trying to work out the mean number of parking tickets he has issued per day. He produced the table below, but has accidentally rubbed out some of the numbers.

i. Fill in the missing numbers

8 Marks

Tickets per day	frequency	Tickets per day $\times$ frequency
0	1	
1		1
2	10	
3	7	
4		20
5	2	
6		
Totals	26	72

HOLY FAMILY NURSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – JULY, 2020
(PBM2) STA 221: STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
 - Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
 - Each question carries 20 marks.
 - Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

The table below delineates days spent by patients receiving treatment for COVID-19 at the ward.

Age (years)	40 – 44	45 – 49	50 – 54	55 – 59	60 – 64
Frequency (f)	2	3	5	6	4

Calculate

- a. The median day spent - 8 Marks
- b. The modal day spent - 7 Marks
- 5 Marks for Table**

Question Two

The table below shows the number of hours obtained by 20 nursing students on the ward.

Number of Hours	40 – 44	45 – 49	50 – 54	55 – 59	60 – 64
Number of Students	2	3	7	6	2

From the table, calculate to two decimal places;

- a. Variance. 11 Marks
- b. Standard deviation 3 Marks
- c. Mean 3 Marks
- d. Co-efficient of variation. 3 Marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2018

RGN 20 & RM 15 STA: 121 STATISTICS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

The table below indicates the ages of 20 patients at the General Ward of the Holy Family Hospital, Techiman. Ages (years)

Age (years)	5- 9	10 -14	15 - 19	20 -24	25 - 29
Frequency	2	4	8	5	1

- a. Construct a histogram for the distribution. - 9 Marks
- b. Use the graph to estimate the mode. - 1 Mark
- c. State two (2) advantages of the mode - 2 Marks
- d. State three (3) types of bar charts - 3 Marks
- e. State two (2) similarities between a bar chart and a histogram - 2 Marks
- f. In a tabular form state three (3) differences between a bar chart and a histogram - 3 Marks

Question Two

The marks obtained by students in a statistics test are given below

77 18 63 84 38 54 50 59 60 60
54 56 36 26 50 34 44 41 71 61
58 58 53 51 62 43 52 53 61 52
63 62 62 65 45 66 83 71 63 58

- a. Copy and complete the following frequency table for the distribution - 15 Marks

Class	Frequency (f)	Class mark (x)	fx	Class Boundary	Relative Frequency
10 -19	1	14.5	14.5	9.5 – 19.5	0.025
:	:	:	:	:	:
:	:	:	:	:	:
80 -89	2	84.5	169.0	79.5 – 89.5	0.050

- b. Calculate the mean of the distribution, correct to 2 decimal places.

SIGNATURE OF EXAMINER: _____
5 Marks

NAME OF EXAMINER: _____

Question Three

- a. Define the term observation as a tool for collecting data. - 1 Mark
- b. State three (3) advantages of observation as a tool for collecting data - 3 Marks
- c. Explain when each of the following techniques of data collection is most appropriate for data collection (State two in each case)
 - (i) Questionnaire - 2 Marks
 - (ii) Interview - 2 Marks
 - (iii) Observation - 2 Marks
- d. Outline five (5) reasons for sampling. - 5 Marks
- e. (i) Differentiate between probability sampling and non-probability sampling - 2 Marks
- (ii) State three (3) methods each under probability and non-probability sampling - 3 Marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HOLY FAMILY NURSING AND MIDWIFERY TRAINING COLLEGE – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2017
(RGN 19 & RM 14) STA 121: STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

a. Define briefly the following statistical terms

- | | |
|------------------------------|--------|
| i. Covert observation ✓ | 1 Mark |
| ii. Sampling frame | 1 Mark |
| iii. Participant observation | 1 Mark |
| iv. Sampling fraction | 1 Mark |
| v. Hawthorne effect ✓ | 1 Mark |

- b. State four (4) importance of statistics 4 Marks
- c. State four (4) methods of collecting statistical data 4 Marks
- d. A sample is the selected elements chosen for participation in a study. List three (3) reasons for using a sample rather than the entire population in a research. 3 Marks
- e. Sampling methods or procedures can be broken down into two main headings. State them. 2 Marks
- f. State any two (2) methods under each of the headings stated in question e. 2 Marks

Question Two

The table below shows the weight ranges of 100 patients weighed in the Out-Patients Department of the Holy Family Hospital, Techiman.

Weight (kg)	20 – 29	30 – 39	40 – 49	50 – 59	60 – 69	70 – 79
Number of patients	10	18	22	25	16	9

- a. Construct a cumulative frequency table for the distribution 6 Marks
- b. Draw a cumulative frequency curve for the distribution 6 Marks
- c. Use the curve to estimate the median of the distribution 3 Marks
- d. State one (1) advantage of the median 1 Mark
- e. State one (1) disadvantage of the median 1 Mark
- f. In a tabular form state three (3) differences between a bar chart and a pie chart 3 Marks

Question Four

Patients who reported at the children's ward at a clinic on a particular day have their ages in (months) recorded as follows:

10	11	9	10	13	15	13	8	16	12
12	8	12	11	13	9	11	14	10	12
9	8	8	12	9	13	14	11	12	9

- a. i. Construct an ungrouped frequency distribution table for the data. 2 1/2 Marks
- ii. Calculate the mean age to the nearest whole number. 6 1/2 Marks
- iii. Calculate the median age of the children. 4 Marks

- b. Calculate the standard deviation of the following set of scores of a group of students in a class: 9, 10, 10, 12, 12, 13, 15, 15, correcting your answer to 2 decimal places. 7 Marks

NMTC - BERENKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - APRIL 2013
(D15) HRGN 042 / HMDW 028 BASICS STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

The frequency distribution table below is the marks scored in an anatomy examination

Marks	Frequency
24 -28	10
29 -33	18
34 -38	16
39 -43	16
44 -48	11
49- 53	27
54 -58	17
59-63	49
64- 68	22
69-73	6
74-78	8

Calculate from the distribution

- | | | | |
|----|--------------------|---|---------|
| a. | Range | - | 3 marks |
| b. | Mean Deviation | - | 7 marks |
| c. | Variance | - | 7 marks |
| d. | Standard deviation | - | 3 marks |

Question Two

table below shows the ages of 20 students who sat for the statistics End of Semester Examination

Age (yrs)	5 - 9	10 - 14	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29
Frequency (f)	2	3	7	6	2

Find

- | | | | |
|----|------------------------------------|---|---------|
| a. | Mean of the distribution | - | 3 marks |
| b. | The median of the distribution | - | 5 marks |
| c. | The most frequent occurring number | - | 5 marks |
| d. | The Semi - interquartile range | - | 7 marks |

Question Three

A sample of 180 head pans was selected at random from a factory by a building firm. The table below shows the number of times the pans were borrowed by labourers in one year.

<i>No of labourers</i>	<i>No of head pans</i>
0 -5	9
6- 10	20
11- 15	32
16 - 20	42
21 - 25	35
26 - 30	15
31 - 35	22
36 - 40	5

- a. State the modal class 2 marks

- b. Draw a cumulative frequency curve to illustrate the distribution 10 marks
 - Table 5 marks
 - Graph 3 marks

- c. From the graph, estimate the median mark

NMTC – BEREKUM/ ST. MARY’S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2016
(D18) HRGN 042, HMDW 028: BASIC STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

a. State the term that best describe the approach used by the researcher in the under listed research or scenarios:

5 Marks

1. A researcher wanted to study the behavior of nurses towards the care of elderly stroke patients in the Holy Family Hospital, Berekum. In doing so the researcher mixed with the nurses undetected and observed their behavior towards the patients.
2. A researcher wanted to determine the effects of marijuana on the brain and body of marijuana addicts. In selecting his samples, the researcher initially identified one addict and asked the addict to recruit other people.
3. A researcher wanted to study the effects of prolonged hours of teaching on the academic performance of students at the Holy Family NMTC, Berekum. He declared his motives to the students and gained their permission at the beginning of the study. While observing them, the researcher performed every activity the students were performing.
4. A researcher wanted to study the perception and attitude of pregnant women in Berekum towards antenatal visits. In collecting his data, he designed series of questions and gave it to the pregnant women to fill and return them after completion.
5. A researcher wanted to study the role of asphyxia prevention and management in the reduction of neonatal mortality at the Holy Family Hospital Berekum. The researcher selected the obstetricians and midwives at the hospital to form his sample because he believed that they will give him the desired or accurate information he needed.

- b. State the steps adopted in statistical analysis or methods in the right order. - 6 Marks
- c. State any four (4) reasons for using samples rather than the entire population. - 4 Marks
- d. In not more than **30 words** differentiate between target population and accessible population. - 2 Marks
- e. State any three (3) probability sampling techniques. - 3 Marks

Question Two

a. Patients who reported at a children's ward at a clinic on a particular day have their ages in (months) recorded as follows:

10 11 9 10 13 15 13 8 16 12
12 8 12 11 13 9 11 14 10 12
9 8 8 12 9 13 14 11 12 9

- i. Construct an ungrouped frequency distribution table for the data. - 3 Marks
- ii. Use your table to calculate the mean age to the nearest whole number. - 6 Marks
- iii. Calculate the median age of the children. - 4 Marks
- iv. Calculate the standard deviation of the following set of scores of a group of students in a class 9, 10, 10, 12, 12, 13, 15, 15, correcting your answer to 2 decimal places. - 7 Marks

Question Three

The ages of 20 patients at the Emergency Unit of the St. Mary's Hospital, Drobo are as follows;

Age (years)	40 - 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59	60 - 64
Frequency	2	3	7	6	2

Calculate from the distribution;

- a. Range - 2 Marks
- b. Mean deviation - 7 Marks
- c. Variance - 7 Marks
- d. Standard deviation - 3 Marks
- e. What is the modal class of the distribution? - 1 Mark

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – APRIL 2013
(D15) HRGN 042 / HMDW 028 BASICS STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
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Question One

The frequency distribution table below is the marks scored in an anatomy examination

Marks	Frequency
24 -28	10
29 -33	18
34 -38	16
39 -43	16
44 -48	11
49- 53	27
54 -58	17
59-63	49
64- 68	22
69-73	6
74-78	8

- Calculate from the distribution
- | | | | |
|----|--------------------|---|---------|
| a. | Range | - | 3 marks |
| b. | Mean Deviation | - | 7 marks |
| c. | Variance | - | 7 marks |
| d. | Standard deviation | - | 3 marks |

Question Two

The table below shows the ages of 20 students who sat for the statistics End of Semester Examination

Age (yrs)	5 - 9	10 - 14	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29
Frequency (f)	2	3	7	6	2

Find

- | | | | |
|----|------------------------------------|---|---------|
| a. | Mean of the distribution | - | 3 marks |
| b. | The median of the distribution | - | 5 marks |
| c. | The most frequent occurring number | - | 5 marks |
| d. | The Semi – interquartile range | - | 7 marks |

Question Three

A sample of 180 head pans was selected at random from a factory by a building firm. The table below shows the number of times the pans were borrowed by labourers in one year.

<i>No of labourers</i>	<i>No of head pans</i>
0 -5	9
6- 10	20
11- 15	32
16 - 20	42
21 - 25	35
26.- 30	15
31 - 35	22
36 - 40	5

- a. State the modal class - 2 marks

- b. Draw a cumulative frequency curve to illustrate the distribution
 - Table - 10 marks
 - Graph - 5 marks

- c. From the graph, estimate the median mark - 3 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2016
(D18) HRGN 042, HMDW 028: BASIC STATISTICS
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. State the term that best describe the approach used by the researcher in the under listed research or scenarios: 5 Marks
1. A researcher wanted to study the behavior of nurses towards the care of elderly stroke patients in the Holy Family Hospital, Berekum. In doing so the researcher mixed with the nurses undetected and observed their behavior towards the patients.
 2. A researcher wanted to determine the effects of marijuana on the brain and body of marijuana addicts. In selecting his samples, the researcher initially identified one addict and asked the addict to recruit other people.
 3. A researcher wanted to study the effects of prolonged hours of teaching on the academic performance of students at the Holy Family NMTC, Berekum. He declared his motives to the students and gained their permission at the beginning of the study. While observing them, the researcher performed every activity the students were performing.
 4. A researcher wanted to study the perception and attitude of pregnant women in Berekum towards antenatal visits. In collecting his data, he designed series of questions and gave it to the pregnant women to fill and return them after completion.
 5. A researcher wanted to study the role of asphyxia prevention and management in the reduction of neonatal mortality at the Holy Family Hospital Berekum. The researcher selected the obstetricians and midwives at the hospital to form his sample because he believed that they will give him the desired or accurate information he needed.
- b. State the steps adopted in statistical analysis or methods in the right order. 6 Marks
- c. State any four (4) reasons for using samples rather than the entire population. 4 Marks
- d. In not more than 30 words differentiate between target population and accessible population. 2 Marks
- e. State any three (3) probability sampling techniques 3 Marks

Question Two

a. Patients who reported at a children's ward at a clinic on a particular day have their ages in (months) recorded as follows:

10	11	9	10	13	15	13	8	16	12
12	8	12	11	13	9	11	14	10	12
9	8	8	12	9	13	14	11	12	9

- i. Construct an ungrouped frequency distribution table for the data. - 3 Marks
- ii. Use your table to calculate the mean age to the nearest whole number. - 6 Marks
- iii. Calculate the median age of the children. - 4 Marks
- iv. Calculate the standard deviation of the following set of scores of a group of students in a class 9, 10, 10, 12, 12, 13, 15, 15, correcting your answer to 2 decimal places. - 7 Marks

Question Three

The ages of 20 patients at the Emergency Unit of the St. Mary's Hospital, Drobo are as follows;

Age (years)	40 - 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59	60 - 64
Frequency	2	3	7	6	2

Calculate from the distribution;

- a. Range - 2 Marks
- b. Mean deviation - 7 Marks
- c. Variance - 7 Marks
- d. Standard deviation - 3 Marks
- e. What is the modal class of the distribution? - 1 Mark